

GENERAL INFORMATION ON THE IMPORTANCE OF FEEDSTOCK DENSITY AND SPEED IN THE FIBER SEPARATION PROCESS

Madumarov Sanjarbek Rustamjonovich¹

Jurayev Yuldashon Yunuskhon Ugli²

Yuldashev Khasanboy Sulayman corner³

Email: c* Corresponding author:

yoldashev93992020@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7229260>

Abstract. It has been known for a long time in the practice of cotton ginning that productivity, raw material density, and fiber quality are closely related to ginning, which is the most important technological process in cotton ginning.

I.G. Boldinsky [4] proved in his research that the increase in gin productivity necessarily occurs with an increase in the density of raw materials.

But with increasing density, productivity increases up to a certain limit and then productivity starts to decrease. This situation is related to the decrease in the speed of rotation of the raw material under the influence of lateral stresses, and the process stops completely when the density is $550 \div 600 \text{ kg / m}^3$. Miroshnichenko proved [5].

Keywords: Cleaning, seed cotton, screen-rod, spiked-cylinder, trash, large contamination, moisture, friction

Introduction. A.D. Grober carried out theoretical and experimental studies on the study of the characteristics and mathematical representation of the aging process. He [6] determined the statistical regularities of the demonization process. In particular, the author showed that reducing the unevenness of the transfer of cotton to the gin working chamber and stabilizing the ginning process improves the quality indicators of cotton fiber.

The analysis of the development of basic research of sawing makes it possible to determine the ways of its optimization. It is necessary to stabilize the ginning process to increase productivity and improve fiber quality.

Materials and Methods. In the practice of cotton factories, the density of the raw material during ginning is subjectively set and adjusted. For this, the supply of gin is set to a speed determined by experience depending on the type of cotton, and then the density of the raw material and the seed goes on to straighten the hairy gin. B.I. Bekmirzaev [7] obtained experimental data on the influence of raw material density on fiber and seed quality (see Table 1.1). From them, it can be seen that the least fiber damage is observed in I-type cotton when the raw material density is 325 kg / m^3 , and in III-type cotton - when it is 290 kg / m^3 (see Figure 1.2).

Table 1.1.

I - and III -type medium fiber cotton

1st-grade cotton		III cotton	
The density of raw material, kg / m ³	In fiber number of demonic drugs, % _ _	The raw material of the governor density, kg / m ³	In fiber number of demonic drugs, % _ _
171.8	2.12	183.6	3.1
196.4	1.67	248.1	2.05
314.9	1.24	255.7	1.97
326.3	1.15	280.5	1.96
328.2	1.33	288.2	1.94
344.5	1.81	293.9	1.86
349.2	2.48	301.5	2.02
364.5	2.73	314.9	2.35
		337.8	2.8
		351.1	3.04

S. Fazildinov, R.M. In Kattakhodjaev's scientific article [8], the reasons for the increase in the mass fraction of fiber defects and impurities in the mass fraction of large chaff, straw, fibrous bark, and broken seeds after cotton ginning and the role of raw material density in them were examined.

Results and Discussions. The research conducted at JSC "Pakhtasanoat Scientific Center" and TTESI showed that the main reason for the formation of warping defects in fiber is an excessive and variable amount of raw materials.

a)

b)

Figure 1.2. Dependence of the number of fiber defects (fiber husks, combined knots, knots, and knots) on the density of the raw material (a and b, respectively) in the ginning of I- and III-type cotton.

is the density. When the density of the raw material increases, bad knots, combined knots, and knots are formed in the weaving process. To reduce ginning defects, the ginning process should be carried out in a relatively loose and stable density of the raw material. The authors investigated the quality of fiber obtained from gin when the density was reduced using the raw material.

The experiments used 108F I-grade hand-picked cotton with 7.2% moisture and 0.4% contamination before ginning. The results of the elastic element saw gin work of the raw material shaft with the optimal diameter of 150 mm and speed of 230 rpm were compared with the 3XDD-M gin work indicators.

Table 1.2.

Effect of raw material density on defects in spun yarn

Gin productivity, kg/saw-hour	Mass of raw material, kg	The density of raw material, kg / m ³	Mass percentage of defects and impurities, %			
			Total	Broken seed and fibrous bark	A broken seed	Fibrous bark
Raw material density is normal						
8.8	55.3	354	2.60	1.20	0.29	0.91
10.1	64.1	410	2.73	1.30	0.36	0.94
12.3	67.8	430	2.81	1.37	0.38	0.99
The density of the raw material is reduced						
8.6	39.2	300	2.05	0.81	0.15	0.66
13.8	43.5	309	2.15	0.90	0.17	0.73
15.6	44.4	312	2.13	0.93	0.20	0.73
17.3	46.8	314	2.18	0.99	0.25	0.74

With the increase in productivity, the density of the raw material also increases, which leads to an increase in deformation defects. When comparing the work of two gins, it can be seen that as a result of reducing the density of raw materials, the mass fraction of defects and impurities decreases by 0.5-0.6% mainly due to ginning defects.

Conclusion. According to the conclusions of the authors based on the results of the experiment, it is necessary to reduce the density of the raw material to reduce the deformation defects. The data of the spinning laboratory of the "Cotton Industry Scientific Center" JSC on the quality of yarn spun from the obtained fiber also confirms this opinion (see Table 1.2).

density and speed parameters of the raw material during sawing process depend on the balance between the intensity of supply and the process of excretion of purified seed. Accordingly, we have familiarized ourselves with the

main studies carried out on the issues of ensuring ginning and the issue of fiber and seed release.

References:

- [1] HT Ahmedkhojayev, M. A. Tojiboyev, KhNSharipov "Improving the fiber separation process" "Talent ziyo press" Namangan-2021
- [2] O. Sh. Sarimsakov "Theoretical bases of cotton transfer and pneumatic transport processes" Tashkent-2021
- [3] Mukhsinov I, Isayev Sh, Yuldashev H. "Theoretical analysis of the motion of raw cotton with uniform feeder in a cotton cleaner" The American Journal of Engineering and Technology (ISSN – 2689-0984) Published: January 22, 2021, | Pages: 13-20
- [4] Sulayman A Inamove M, Yuldashev KH "Theoretical studies of the nature of the interaction of cotton seeds in the gap between the agitator blade and the saw cylinder" Eurasian journal of academic research, Pages 666-672 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7218857>
- [5] Jurayev Y, Tukhtaev Sh, Yuldashev KH, "Investigation of fiber loss in impurities from the ss-15a separator" Eurasian journal of academic research, volume 2 Issue 11, October 2022 ISSN 2181-2020 425-431 Pages <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7193675>
- [6] Sarimsakov O, Kurbanov D, Jurayev Y, Yuldashev KH "Investigation of losing fiber during cleaning cotton" Modern in the world practical subjects: problems and solutions » named scientific, remote, online conference, pp. 101-109 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6559924>
- [7] Sharipov X, Yuldashev KH, Jurayev Y, Urinboyev B "Research of losing fiber cleaner technologies and foreign lint cleaner technologies" Modern in the world practical sciences: problems and solutions _ _ scientific, remote, online conference, pp. 91-100 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6559910>
- [8] Dusmatov. A Yuldashev KH, "Cotton to keep preparation the device small and large from impurities cleaning process theoretical study "Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences Volume 1 | Issue 5 ISSN 2181-1784, Scientific Journal
- [9] Sarimsakov O, Sharapova X, Yuldashev KH, Madumarov S "Investigation of separation of usable fibers added to contamination infants during cleaning cotton" in Uzbekistan interdisciplinary innovation and scientific studies magazine No. 8, May 20, 2022, pages 448-455,

